

IN VITRO EVALUATION OF FUNGICIDES AGAINST *Sphaceloma rosarum*

S. L. Badgujar, 2 P. M. Khandare, 3 S. P. Gadewad 4 S.D. Shewale

1 Head Department of Plant Pathology, VNMKV, Parbhani.

2. Assistant Professor Department of Plant Pathology, VNMKV, Parbhani.

3. Assistant Professor Department of Plant Pathology, MPKV Rahuri.

4. Department of Plant Pathology, VNMKV, Parbhani.

padma.khandare@rediffmail.com

MS Received: 26.05.2024; MS Revised:30.06.2024; MS Accepted:01.07.2024

MS 3225

(RESEARCH PAPER IN PLANT PATHOLOGY,)

Abstract

Among the nine fungicides evaluated in in vitro against *Sphaceloma rosarum*, systemic fungicide; Thiophanate methyl, Non-systemic fungicides viz., Copper oxychloride, combination fungicide was Carbendazim 12%+ Mancozeb 63% showed antifungal or fungistatic with total inhibition of mycelial growth at the concentration of Systemic fungicides 500 and 1000 ppm, non- systemic and combi fungicides 1500 and 2000 ppm. However, all the fungicides showed inhibition of fungal growth at 2000 ppm concentration.

Keywords : *Sphaceloma rosarum*, Fungicides, Rose, Thiophanate.

Introduction

Rose belongs to kingdom Plantae, Order Rosales, Family Rosaceae, Sub Family Rosoideae and Genus Rosa (Basu *et al.*, 2015). There are around 150 species in the genus Rosa, and they are widely distributed (MacPhail and Kevan, 2009). Roses may flourish in many different types of environments, including fields, salty or freshwater marshes, roadsides, and temperate forests (Hummer and Janick, 2009). Rose has numerous illnesses brought on by germs, viruses, and fungi. The bacterial diseases crown gall (*Agrobacterium tumefaciens*), viral diseases rose mosaic (PNRSV), die-back (*Diplodia rosarum*), black spot (*Diplocarpon rosae*), botrytis blight (*Botrytis cinera*), cankers (*Coniothyrium fuckelli*), powdery mildew (*Sphaeretheca pannosa*), downy mildew (*Pernospora sparsa*), rust (*Phragmidis disciflorura*), die-back (*Diplodia rosarum*), black spot (*Diplocarpon rosae*), illnesses caused by bacteria, such as crown gall (*Agrobacterium tumefaciens*), cankers (*Coniothyrium fuckelli*), rose mosaic (PNRSV), rose rosette (*Rose rosette virus*), and botrytis blight (*Botrytis cinera*) Pal, (1966) and Sinha, (2017)}. *Sphaceloma rosarum* is the cause of anthracnose, one of the most prevalent illnesses affecting roses. Italy provided the first account of anthracnose on roses in 1881. It was first documented on wild roses in the United States in 1898. According to Ong (2015), the disease known by the common name anthracnose is brought on by a group of fungi that induce comparable symptoms in

a variety of host plants, including numerous types of trees and shrubs. The fungus *Sphaceloma rosarum* causes anthracnose on roses, which manifests as a range of symptoms including patches on the leaves of affected plants. It could result in significant defoliation if left untreated. There were tiny reddish-purple stains on the veins of the leaves. Eventually, the spots got black, and the border was surrounded by a thin brown margin. Unlike the feathery margins of black dots, the edges of leaf spots were defined and smooth. Shot-hole lesions were left behind when the leaf spots' centers became gray and eventually fell out. The leaves prematurely dropped, wilted, and became yellow. *In vitro* evaluation of fungicide provides preliminary information regarding its efficacy against a pathogen within a shortest period of time and therefore, serves a guide for further field testing hence the present investigation was undertaken to screen a range of fungicide, including new chemical formulation for their ability to inhibit the mycelia growth of *in vitro*.

Material And Methods

An experiment was conducted during 2021 at Department of Plant Pathology, VNMKV, Parbhani. To find out the effective fungicide against *Sphaceloma rosarum* *in vitro*. The experiment was designed Completely Randomized Design (CRD) with three replication and ten treatments.

Table A: Different Fungicides with their chemical and trade name

Sr. No.	Chemical name	TradeName	Concentration(ppm)
Systemic fungicides			
T1	Azoxystrobin 23 EC	Amitsar Top	500, 1000
T2	Hexaconazole 5 WP	Contaf	500, 1000
T3	Thiophanate Methyl 70 WP	Topsin M	500, 1000
Non-Systemic fungicides			
T4	Chlorothalonil 75 WP	Kavach	1500, 2000
T5	Propineb 70 WP	Anthracol	1500, 2000
T6	Copper oxychloride 50 WP	Blitox	1500, 2000
Combi Fungicides			
T7	Carbendazim 12% % + Mancozeb 63%	SAAF	1500, 2000
T8	Hexaconazole 4 % +Zineb 68% (75%WP)	Avtar	1500, 2000
T9	Metalaxyl M 4%+Mancozeb 64% (68%WP)	Redomil	1500, 2000
T10	Control	-----	-----

Efficacy of three systemic fungicides (@ 500, 1000 ppm) and three non-systemic fungicides (@ 1500, 2000 ppm) and three combined fungicides (@ 1500 and 2000 ppm) was evaluated *in vitro* against *Sphaceloma rosarum* by poisoned food technique (Nene and Thapliyal, 1993). The detail of the fungicides used are given in Table A. Based on active ingredient, the requisite quantity of each fungicide was calculated and mixed thoroughly with autoclaved and cooled (40°C) Potato dextrose agar medium (PDA) in conical flasks to obtain desired concentrations of (500, 1000), (1500, 2000) and (1500, 2000)

ppm for systemic, non- systemic, combined fungicides respectively. Fungicide amended with PDA medium was then poured (20 ml/plate) aseptically in Petri plates (90 mm dia.) and allowed to solidify at room temperature. For each test fungicide and its test concentration, three plates / treatment / replication were maintained and replicated thrice. After solidification of the medium, all the plates were inoculated aseptically with a 5 mm culture disc obtained from a week old actively growing pure culture of *Sphaceloma rosarum*. The culture disc was placed on PDA in inverted position in the centre of

the Petri plate and plates were incubated at 28 °C. Petri plates filled with plain PDA (without any fungicide) and inoculated with the culture disc of the test pathogen were maintained as control (untreated). Observations on radial mycelial growth/colony diameter of the pathogen were recorded at 24 hours interval and continued till the untreated control plate was fully covered with mycelial growth of the test pathogen. Per cent mycelial growth inhibition of the test pathogen with the test fungicides over untreated control was calculated by applying the formula given by Vincent (1927).

Where,

$$R = \{(C - T) / C\} \times 100$$

C= Growth (mm) of test fungus in untreated control plate

T = Growth (mm) of test fungus in treated plates

Result And Discussion

In vitro evaluation of different chemical against *Sphaceloma rosarum* was done as described in material and methods using following poisoned food technique. The fungicide were tested 3 systemic fungicides at 500, 1000 ppm concentration and 3 non-systemic fungicides at 1500 and 2000 ppm concentration and 3 combination fungicides at 1500, 2000 ppm concentration each and the observation on colony diameter and percent inhibition of colony growth over control are presented in Table 1 and Plate 1. All the tested systemic fungicides exhibited a wide range of radial mycelial growth of *Sphaceloma rosarum* over untreated control (90.00 mm) and the mycelial growth was found to decrease drastically with increase in concentrations of the fungicides tested. However, the Systemic fungicide; Thiophanate methyl 70 WP at 500 ppm concentration significantly inhibited the mycelial growth up to 90.13 per cent and 92.67 per cent at 1000 ppm concentration. Non-systemic fungicides viz., Copper oxychloride 50 WP, Chlorothalonil 75 WP, Propineb 70

WP, each @ 1500 ppm recorded 88.00, 76.98 and 59.56 per cent inhibition of the *Sphaceloma rosarum*, respectively. While, at 2000 ppm concentration, Copper oxychloride 50 WP, Chlorothalonil 75 WP and Propineb 70 WP showed significant mycelial growth inhibition of *Sphaceloma rosarum* at 91.48, 87.25 and 68.27 per cent, respectively. The best combination fungicide @ 1500 ppm concentration was Carbendazim 12%+ Mancozeb 63% WP inhibited 94.44 per cent mycelial growth of *Sphaceloma rosarum*. At 2000 ppm concentration, mycelial growth inhibition of *Sphaceloma rosarum* recorded for all the three combination fungicides was same viz., Carbendazim 12% + Mancozeb 63%, Hexaconazole 4% + Zineb 68% WP and Metalaxyl 8% + Mancozeb 64% WP was 94.44 per cent. Therefore, it was discovered that every fungicide examined was fungistatic against *Sphaceloma rosarum* and that it greatly slowed down the parasite's mycelial growth in comparison to the untreated control. The current results were consistent with those of Ekbote (2005), who found that against *C. capsici* of chilli anthracnose, propiconazole (0.05%) was much better than all other treatments. Hexaconazole (0.10%), Chlorothalonil (0.15%), and Azoxystrobin (0.15%) were the next best treatments. According to Prashanth (2007), Mancozeb + Carbendazim was more effective at stopping *C. gloeosporioides* mycelial growth in anthracnose cases. Bagade *et al.* (2020) noted that the effectiveness of six fungicides against infections was assessed using the poisoned food technique. The best treatments for stopping 100% mycelial development were carbendazim + Mancozeb (@0.25%) and carbboxin + Thiram (@0.3%), which were followed by pyraclostrobin (91.48%), copper oxychloride (88.55%), and propineb (72.22%). Least mycelial growth inhibition observed in Azoxystrobin (54.44%).

Table 1. *In vitro* efficacy of fungicides against mycelial growth and inhibition of *Sphaceloma rosarum*

Tr No.	Chemical Name	Col. dia. *(mm) at Conc.		Per cent Inhibition*	
		500 ppm	1000 ppm	500 ppm	1000 ppm
Systemic fungicides					
T1	Azoxystrobin 23 EC	80.40	71.41	10.65 (19.04)	20.64 (27.02)
T2	Hexaconazole 5 EC	16.33	14.44	81.85 (64.78)	83.95 (66.38)
T3	Thiophanate methyl 70 WP	8.88	6.57	90.13 (71.68)	92.67 (74.29)
Non-systemic fungicides		1500 Ppm	2000 Ppm	1500 ppm	2000 ppm
T4	Chlorothalonil 75WP	20.70	11.47	76.98 (61.32)	87.25 (69.07)
T5	Propineb 70 WP	36.38	28.55	59.56 (50.51)	68.27 (55.71)
T6	Copper oxychloride 50 WP	10.80	7.66	88.00 (69.73)	91.48 (73.02)
Combination fungicides		1500 Ppm	2000 Ppm	1500 ppm	2000 ppm
T7	Carbendazim 12%+ Mancozeb 63% WP	5.00	5.00	94.44 (76.36)	94.44 (76.36)
T8	Hexaconazole 4% + Zineb 68% WP	17.51	5.00	80.53 (63.81)	94.44 (76.36)
T9	Metalaxyl M4% + Mancozeb 64% WP	8.48	5.00	90.57 (72.11)	94.44 (76.36)
T10	Control	90.00	90.00	0.00	0.00
	SE(m) ±	0.516	0.447	0.516	0.447
	C.D. (P=0.05)	1.534	1.329	1.534	1.329

*Mean of three replications. Dia: Diameter

(Figures in parenthesis are arc sine transformed value)

T₁- Azoxystrobin 23 EC

T₂- Hexaconazole 5 WP

T₃- Hexaconazole 4% + Zineb 68%

T₄- Chlorothalonil 75 WP

T₁₀- Control

T₆- Copper oxychloride 50 WP

T₇- Carbedazim 12% + Mancozeb 63%

T₃- Thiophanate Methyl 70 WP

T₉- Metalaxyl M4% + Mancozeb 64%

T₅- Propineb 70 WP

Plate 1 Efficacy of fungicides against *Sphaceloma rosarum*

References

1. Basu, S. K., Zandi, P., Cetzal-Ix, W. and Sengupta, R. (2015). The genus *Rosa* An aristocrat from plant family with class, colour and fragrance, *Iranian Society of Environmentalists*, IRSEN Newsletter.
2. Bagade, A. R., Giri, G. K., Shingne, A. W. and Usendi, P. N. (2020). *In vitro* evaluation of fungicides, botanicals and bio-agents against *Colletotrichum lindemuthianum* causing anthracnose of bean, *Int. J. Curr. Microbiol. App. Sci.* 9 (8), 3103-3110.
3. Ekbote, S. D. (2005). Management of chilli fruit rot caused by *Colletotrichum capsici*. *J. Mycol Plant. Pathol*, 35(1), 183-185.
4. Hummer, K.E. and Janick J. (2009). Rosaceae: Taxonomy, economic importance and genomics, *Springer Science*, 1-17.
5. MacPhail, V. J., and Kevan, P. G. (2009). Review of the breeding systems of wild roses (*Rosa spp.*), *Floriculture and Ornamental Biotechnology*, 3 (1), 1-13.
6. Nene, Y. L. and Thapliyal, P. N. (1993). Evaluation of fungicides Plant Disease Control (3" od.) Oxford, IBH Pub. Co. Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi. 531-532.
7. Ong, K. (2015). Rose anthracnose. *Agri life extention. tamu. edu.*, 9, 15.
8. Pal, B.P. (1966). The rose in India, *Indian Council of Agricultural Research*, 161-170.
9. Patil N.P., Ambadkar C.V., Shinde V. N and J.D.Deshmukh, 2018, In Vitro Evaluation Of Fungicides Against Plasmopara Viticola Causing Downy Mildew Of Grape, Volume V, Issue XV JAN 2016 Multilogic In Science ISSN 2277-7601, Page 283-287.
10. Prashanth, A. (2007). Investigations on anthracnose of pomegranate (*Colletotrichum gloeosporioides* Penz.) Penz. And Sacc. *Karnataka J. Agric. Sci.*, 20 (4), 929.
11. Sinha, R. (2017). Study on rose diseases identification, detection and cure. *International Journal of Engineering Development and Research*, 5 (2), 292-295.
12. Vincent, J. M. (1927). A Manual for the practical study of root nodule bacteria. IBP handbook No.15, Blackwall, Sci. Pub. Oxford 77.